

Research Article

Online Exam Portal System Using Machine Learning Algorithm

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Abstract— According to today's requirements, an Online Examination System is critical for educational institutions to organize tests, since it saves time and effort in checking exam papers and preparing result reports. Because the present state of technology makes offline examinations almost unfeasible, online methods should be enhanced to conduct any exams that require evaluation of a candidate's hearing, reading, writing, or speaking abilities. Online Examination Portal with Machine Learning Concepts is a web-based examination system that allows students to take exams online with the purpose of comprehensively evaluating them using a fully automated method that not only saves time but also provides quick and accurate results. This approach assesses a student's listening, reading, speaking, and writing abilities.

Exam Portal with Machine Learning Ideas is a Python online application that includes machine learning concepts like as spell checking, language provision evaluation, and exploratory data analysis.

This web application keeps track of applicant logins and test attendance in many categories such as multiple choice questions, descriptive questions, audio listening, and so on.

Their report and progress will be presented in a graphical and statistical format. The application's major goal is to incorporate machine learning into the examinations to make them more sophisticated and user-friendly. This tool may be used to challenge any form of written exam. This

website may also be used by students who are studying for examinations to practise and track their progress

Keywords— Machine Learning, Python, Web-based examination system

I. INTRODUCTION

An online examination portal is a web-based examination system that incorporates machine learning concepts. Exams are available online with the goal of finishing them quickly. Examine the student thoroughly using a different approach. An automated process that not only saves time but also produces accurate and timely results.

Private institutes as well as educational institutions might employ an online examination method. Online examinations are a terrific method to keep momentum in higher education and guarantee the learning process doesn't come to a standstill during a time when in-person exams are fraught with dangers owing to Covid-19. In this situation, more modern methods are required to perform all types of tests. Our project is an online test system that can assess a candidate's abilities to listen, write, and

speak. Advanced tests, like as IELTS, use such evaluations, which had hitherto been completed offline.

This tool may be used to challenge any written examination. This website may also be used by students who are studying for examinations to practise and track their progress.

According to today's requirements, a web-based examination system with Machine learning concepts is a web-based examination system where examinations are given online, with the goal of effectively evaluating the student thoroughly exams, saving the time and effort required to check the exam papers and prepare result reports. Because the present state of technology makes offline examinations almost unfeasible, online solutions should be enhanced to conduct any exams that involve evaluating a candidate's listening, writing, or speaking competence. The Online Assessment Portal with Machine Learning Concepts is a web-based examination system in which exams are administered online with the purpose of comprehensively evaluating the student. This approach assesses a student's listening, reading, and speaking abilities. Exam Portal with Machine Learning Ideas is a Python online application that includes machine learning concepts like as spell checking, language provision evaluation, and exploratory data analysis. This web application keeps track of applicant logins and test attendance in many categories such as multiple choice questions, descriptive questions, audio listening, and so on. Their report and progress will be presented in a graphical and statistical format. The application's major goal is to incorporate machine learning into the examinations to make them more sophisticated and user-friendly. This tool may be used to challenge any written examination. This website may also be used by students who are studying for examinations to practise and monitor their progress.

II. METHODOLOGY

The Online Examination System is a Python-based online programme that assesses a candidate's listening, writing, and speaking abilities at various levels.

The candidate has the option of creating an account and logging in as needed. A timer is used to keep track of the exam. The database stores candidate login information, test results, and other information. The test results and progress will be shown at the conclusion of the test, as well as in the dashboard. Natural language processing, exploratory data analysis, and other machine learning principles are applied in this application.

II.a. Listening

The first section of the test will be this. The audio of a contents paragraph explaining a scenario or providing information will be played. This recording will be kept in the database.

Only the administrator has access to the audio file. The candidate must next respond to a series of questions relating to the audio. The answers are then compared to the database, and the results are recorded. This will provide an accurate assessment of the candidate's listening capacity.

II.b. Speaking

The candidate is required to talk in English on a certain topic. The speech will be captured and fed into the speechat code as an input. It collects prosody features from real-time or recorded speech streams, performs features engineering, and builds a dataset. The dataset is then fed into machine learning algorithms, which predict intonations, prosody, stress, and spoken language structures. It scripts the speech and transmits it to a language model for additional analysis to quantify pragmatic and emotive emotions, as well as mechanical and structural patterns of speech, using an ASR engine.

II.c. Reading

This is the final step in the procedure. We included three different sorts of questions. The first step is to read the supplied phrase and respond to the multiple choice questions based on it. The second one is based on fill-in-the-blank questions. The third is focused on putting

II.d. System Design

This web application keeps track of applicant logins and test attendance in many categories such as multiple choice questions, descriptive questions, audio listening, and so on. This approach assesses a student's listening, reading, and speaking abilities. The application's major goal is to incorporate machine learning into the examinations to make them more sophisticated and user-friendly.

There exists mainly 2 users.

a).The candidates: They are the ones who is attending exams and viewing the results

b).The admins: They are the ones who set the question papers and manipulate the contents of the application.

Users typically register for the application or login (if already registered), answer the questions, submit the paper, and check the results. This application is more concerned with the applicants' user experience than with the admins'. The database already contains the questions that the student must answer.

The database also stores the replies and other inputs. The programme is generally accessed by the administrators.

Their primary responsibility is to create the questions. Adding, editing, examining, and removing questions are all part of the question-setting process. Other administrative duties include reviewing student applications and announcing results, among others.

III. RESULT

In today's environment, technology is extremely vital. The Online Examination System is critical to the educational institution's test preparation, since it saves time and effort in reviewing exam papers and preparing result reports. Because the present state of technology makes offline examinations almost unfeasible, online methods should be enhanced to conduct any exams that require evaluation of a candidate's hearing, reading, writing, or speaking abilities. This web application keeps

track of applicant logins and test attendance in many categories such as multiple choice questions, descriptive questions, audio listening, and so on. The application's major goal is to apply machine learning to make the tests more advanced and user-friendly.

This tool may be used to challenge any written examination. This website may also be used by students who are studying for examinations to practise and monitor their progress.

IV. CONCLUSION

According to today's requirements, an Online Examination System is critical for educational institutions to prepare tests, saving time and effort in the process of reviewing exam papers and preparing result reports. Because the present state of technology makes offline examinations almost unfeasible, online solutions should be enhanced to conduct any exams that involve evaluating a candidate's listening, writing, or speaking competence. Online Examination Portal with Machine Learning Concepts is a web-based examination system that allows students to take exams online with the purpose of comprehensively evaluating them using a fully automated method that not only saves time but also provides quick and accurate results. More questions based on Pearson Tests of English (NB: Academic is a computer-based academic English language test geared at non-native English speakers who desire to study abroad) are planned. Reading, writing, hearing, and speaking are all tested.) After the fundamental job is completed, the API utilised is ineffective in terms of the demand since we need to evaluate the essay in all areas and this API can only repair grammar. We aim to add reading assessment as well, preserving the writing component because there is no API that meets the requirements. We intend to add an extra page to the writing section that indicates which lines have errors and what the errors are.

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VI. REFERENCE

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